

Lipid profile in Primary Open Angle Glaucoma (POAG) a clinical correlation in a series of cases in a tertiary care hospital.

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Introduction -

Blindness is the most dreadful assumption of human beings which not only makes the life miserable but also leaves the patient as a liability to family⁽⁵⁾. Primary Open-angle glaucoma (POAG) is a multifactorial condition characterized by a progressive neurodegenerative disease that leads to glaucomatous optic neuropathy and eventually glaucomatous visual field loss leading to progressive loss of sight⁽³⁾. The irreversible and relatively asymptomatic nature of damage caused by glaucoma makes it a great public challenge than cataract, which is the leading cause of blindness globally and 2nd most leading cause in India⁽⁵⁾⁽¹⁰⁾. Various mechanisms and theories are known to cause primary open angle glaucoma (POAG) and among them metabolic disorders like diabetes, hypertriglyceridemia, hypercholesterolemia are noteworthy⁽³⁾. Patients with a positive family history of the disease, black race, patients with middle or high myopia, patients with diabetes mellitus type 2, artery hypertension, hyperthyroidism, patients with night snoring are predetermined for this disease⁽⁴⁾. The global burden of glaucoma is projected to be 60 million, and it is expected to increase further, with almost half of the patients being Asians. In India, 11.2 million people aged ≥ 40 years are estimated to have glaucoma⁽¹⁾.

Population-based studies have reported varying prevalence rates from 0.4% to 4% for POAG⁽²⁾. According to a study, about 111.8 million people will be affected with glaucoma

worldwide by 2040, with majority of cases in Asia and Africa⁽³⁾. The protocol for POAG diagnosis consists of the recommendation for patients over 60 years to be examined for ocular glaucoma once a year, and for patients over 60 years to be examined every three years⁽⁴⁾.

This study aims to evaluate the possible relationship of patient's serum lipid profile to Primary Open Angle Glaucoma.

Methods and materials -

It is case-control study done over period of January 2023 to June 2023.

This study is a case-control study, 30 patients with POAG by clinical tests using standard ophthalmologic examination and equipment and 30 age-matched controls were included and investigated. A fasting Serum lipid profiles was conducted on each subject which includes total cholesterol, serum triglycerides, low-density lipoproteins and high-density lipoproteins (HDLs). These variables were compared and contrasted between the Patients and control groups.

Inclusion Criteria (Cases)-

1. Subjects are chosen as age above 18 years having Primary open angle glaucoma capable of giving voluntarily informed consent.
2. Intraocular pressure above 21 mmHg measured with tonometer.
3. Subjects having visual field defects suggestive of glaucoma.
4. Optic disc changes suggestive related to glaucoma such as thinning of the neuro-retinal rim, increased cup to disc ratio.

Inclusion Criteria (Controls)-

1. Intra Ocular Pressure below 21 mm Hg
2. No glaucomatous changes in optic disc
3. No visual field loss related to glaucoma
4. No pseudo exfoliation material in the capsule of lens or pupil

Exclusion Criteria (Cases) –

1. Patients with history of ocular trauma.
2. Patients who underwent any ocular surgery.
3. Any systemic or local condition causing secondary glaucoma.
4. Patients with medication history of lipid lowering medicines like fibrates, statins

5. Patients with history of diabetes and hypertension.
6. Patients having any retinal pathology.
7. Patients having closed anterior chamber angles.

Exclusion Criteria (Controls) –

1. Patients having myopia (>6D)
2. Patients having any prior history of intraocular surgery, traumatic and complicated cataracts.
3. People on Lipid lowering medications like fibrates, statins.
4. Patients below 18 years of age.
5. Patients having any retinal pathology.
6. Patients having closed AC angles.

Evaluation of patients -

The written informed consent was taken from all the participants.

Demographic data of the participants such as sex, age, address, associated risk factors, and complaints of the participants were recorded.

1. Snellen's chart for visual acuity test
2. Slit lamp for anterior segment examination
3. Goldmann's applanation tonometer for checking IOP.
4. Gonioscopy for checking the structure of the angles.
5. Indirect ophthalmoscope aided funduscopy for checking for any glaucomatous changes.
6. Perimetry testing on zeiss Humphrey field analyzer for any defective visual fields.

Evaluation Method -

1. Eight hour fasting blood samples were taken for serum lipid profile.
2. Total cholesterol, triglycerides (TGL), low density lipoproteins (LDL), and high density lipoproteins (HDL) were the parameters which were looked for in the lipid profile of the patients.
3. Reference values from: National Cholesterol Education Program: Adult Treatment Panel III guidelines 5 (NCEP ATP-III)

4. According to NCEP ATP-III

Hypercholesterolemia: Total Cholesterol > 200 mg/dl

Hypertriglyceridemia : Triglycerides > 150 mg/dl

High LDL : >130 mg/dl

Low HDL : <40 mg/dl

Statistical Analysis -

The demographic parameters are expressed as mean and standard deviation and sex distribution is expressed as frequency and percentage in the two study groups.

Criteria for Significant Results:

1. P value < 0.05: Significant
2. P value <0.001: Highly Significant
3. P value >0.05: Not Significant

Results -

This study included 60 patients among which 30 patients were diagnosed with POAG and other 30 were controls.

Mean age of cases was 63.14 ± 8.23

Lipid Profile	Cases	Controls	P value
1.High Cholesterol	15/30 (50%)	3/30 (10%)	<0.05
2.High Triglycerides	16/30 (53%)	4/30 (13%)	<0.05
3.High LDL	18/30 (60%)	5/30 (17%)	<0.05
4.Low HDL	24/30 (80%)	18/30 (60%)	>0.05

Mean age of controls was 61.88 ± 9.67

Among 30 cases 17(56%) were males and 13(44%) were females and among the 30 controls 14(46%) were males and 16(54%) were females.

PARAMETERS	CASES	CONTROLS
Mean Age	63	61
Gender (Male:Female)	17:13	7:8

Mean values:

PARAMETERS	CASES	CONTROLS	P VALUE
High Cholesterol	205.9±44.85	156.82±9.65	0.012
High Triglycerides	173.83±88.79	113.2±19.3	0.003
High LDL	113.26±37.69	91.71±10.8	0.009
Low HDL	57.9±13.58	48.4±6.83	0.072

Analysis -

1. With the p-values of < 0.05 , the values of Triglycerides, Total cholesterol and LDL were significantly higher in cases than in the control group.
2. It was found that the patients had lower HDL levels than controls, but there was disparity in HDL levels statistically

Discussion -

Abnormal serum lipid levels are correlated with the development of POAG. Increased total cholesterol and triglyceride levels are associated with abnormal lipid metabolism. Deranged lipid levels are a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases ⁽¹⁾.

Our trial shows that there is significant association between high cholesterol levels, high triglyceride levels, high LDL levels with that of Primary Open Angle Glaucoma ⁽¹⁾. Study included 60 patients among which 30 patients were diagnosed with POAG and other 30 were controls. Study showed that with the p-values of < 0.05 , the values of Triglycerides, Total cholesterol and LDL were significantly higher in cases than in the control group and it was found that the patients had lower HDL levels than controls, but there was disparity in HDL levels statistically ⁽⁸⁾.

There are various other studies which show similar results.

1. Study done by Rajesh Joshi and Vaishnavi Adatiya included a total of 100 patients, of whom 50 were diagnosed with POAG (cases) and 50 were controls. High total cholesterol levels (>200 mg/dl) were found in 23 cases (46%) and 8 controls (16%); high serum triglyceride levels (>150 mg/dl) were found in 24 cases (48%) and 7 controls (14%); high LDL levels (130 mg/dl) were found in 28 cases (56%) and 9 controls (18%); and low HDL levels (<40 mg/dl) were found in 38 cases (76%) and 30 controls (60%). The levels of mean cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL were significantly higher in cases than in controls ($P < 0.05$), with a confidence interval (CI) of 95%.
2. Study by Reshma Shaikh, Shefali C Misquith included total of 100 subjects were included in the study .50 cases and 50 age matched controls were considered. Among the cases of POAG, we found that 56% had elevated serum cholesterol levels as compared to 18% of normotensive controls. 52% of glaucoma cases were found to have elevated triglyceride levels as compared to 13% of normotensive controls. 60% of patients with POAG were found to have elevated LDL levels. Levels of total cholesterol, total triglycerides and LDL were significantly higher in cases than in controls with a statistically significant pvalue < 0.05 .
3. Dr.Prachi Dave , Dr.Ashok Kumar Meena and Dr.Jaishree Singh conducted a study which included : This study was conducted on 30 patients with POAG (cases) and 35 individuals without glaucoma (controls).It was seen that high Serum Total Cholesterol (>200 mg/dl) was seen in 19 cases, whereas in controls none of individuals have high cholesterol. High Serum Triglycerides (>150 mg/dl) was seen in 18 cases whereas 3 controls have high triglycerides. Serum LDL-Cholesterol was high (> 130 mg/dl) in 9 cases and 0 controls. Serum HDL-Cholesterol was low (< 40 mg/dl) in 1 case and 6 controls. Serum VLDL-Cholesterol was high (> 30 mg/dl) in 17cases and 4 controls. It shwed that level of total cholesterol, total

triglycerides, LDL cholesterol and VLDL- cholesterol were significantly higher in cases than in controls with p value < 0.05 taking confidence interval 95%.

4. Vijay Kumar T.S.1, Satyendranath Shetty B conducted a study which included. In this study 45 patients of POAG and 45 healthy volunteers were included. Among the participants, High cholesterol (>200 mg/dl) was seen in 22 cases, in controls 8 had high cholesterol. LDL was high (> 130mg/dl) in 25 cases and 9 controls. HDL was (< 40mg/dl) in 29 cases and 15 controls. Levels of total cholesterol, total triglycerides and LDL were significantly high in cases than in controls with P value < 0.05 confidence interval 95%. Level of HDL was lower in cases than in controls but it was not statistically significant ⁽⁶⁾.

5. These findings are comparable to those of Davari *et al.*, who studied 40 patients with POAG and 40 healthy individuals and found that the mean levels of cholesterol (211.18 ± 51.91 mg/dl in cases, 162.38 ± 39.56 mg/dl in controls) and triglyceride (165.92 ± 88.58 mg/dl in cases, 99.46 ± 43.08 mg/dl in controls) were significantly higher in cases than in controls, as was the proportion of patients with hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia and with high LDL levels ⁽¹⁾.

6. Gupta *et al.* conducted a study to assess the relationship between dyslipidaemia and glaucoma in 100 patients with glaucoma and 100 age-matched controls. The levels of total cholesterol, total triglycerides, and LDL were significantly higher in cases than in controls ($P < 0.001$). They concluded that dyslipidaemia is an independent risk factor for POAG ⁽²⁾.

7. Egorow et al. found that patients with glaucoma may have atherogenic hyperlipidaemia with decreased anti-oxidative activity ⁽³⁾.

8. The statins in usage longer than 23 months may significantly reduce the risk of glaucoma was concluded from a study done by McGwin et al ⁽³⁾.

9. In the Beijing eye study14, about 3251 individuals (age>45 years) had their complete ophthalmic examination. Blood serum lipids were also measured. It was found that the patients with dyslipidaemia also had increased Intra Ocular Pressure in them ⁽⁵⁾.

Numerous studies have found a link between hyperlipidemia and POAG. Reactive oxygen species may harm the delicate trabecular meshwork, damage the endothelium of blood vessels that supply the optic nerve head or create atherosclerotic changes due to lipid peroxidation. Increased amounts of cholesterol may also compromise ocular perfusion. Elevated serum lipid concentrations may increase blood viscosity and episcleral venous pressure, restricting the outflow facility ⁽⁶⁾.

Dyslipidemia is a risk factor for POAG. Limitation of the study was the small sample size hence further studies with with a large sample size as well as association of other risk factors should be undertaken ⁽⁹⁾.

Conclusion -

This study shows that dyslipidemia, more specifically

1. High Cholesterol levels
2. High Triglycerides levels
3. High LDL levels are associated with Primary Open Angle Glaucoma as compared to age matched controls. This study provides clinicians with information on adopting multifactorial approach to detect and control hyperlipidaemia and thereby effectively lower the incidence of POAG.

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